

Performance of a Novel Semi Rigid Joist to Stud Web Connection for Light Steel Framed Structures

Sarmad Shakeel^{a,*}, Seyed Mohammad Mojtabaei^b, Buick Davison^a, Alireza Bagheri Sabbagh^c,
Iman Hajirasouliha^a

^aDepartment of Civil and Structural Engineering, The University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK
s.shakeel@sheffield.ac.uk, i.hajirasouliha@sheffield.ac.uk, j.davison@sheffield.ac.uk

^bSchool of Architecture, Building and Civil Engineering, Loughborough University, Leicestershire, UK
m.mojtabaei@lboro.ac.uk

^cSchool of Engineering, University of Aberdeen, Scotland, UK
alireza.bsabbagh@abdn.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Floors in a Light Steel Framed (LSF) structure are supported by joist elements, which are held up by studs. The joist to stud connection is assumed to be a pinned connection in the current ledger framing or platform construction approach. This assumption typically results in deeper joist sections since their design tends to be dictated by bending deformations at mid span under serviceability limit states. This paper investigates the performance of a new type of semi rigid joist to stud web connection, which involves connecting webs of joists and stud joists via screws. The semi-rigidity of the connection enables the transfer of some of the moments from mid spans to supports, and then to studs, which would otherwise be partially utilized. The use of semi rigid connection permits to use of smaller joist sections, which otherwise would not be possible. Through finite element analysis, this study analyses the effects of different connecting element sizes, screw configurations, and gravity loading on the performance of the connection. The performance of the connection is measured in terms of stiffness, bending capacity, and the controlling failure mechanism. A case study design of an LSF building is also shown to highlight the possible advantages of employing the novel semi rigid connection over the currently employed pinned connection.

Keywords: cold formed steel, floor connections, joist to stud connections, semi rigid connection

1 INTRODUCTION

Light steel framed constructions utilize Cold Formed Steel (CFS) components for walls and floors. The walls consist of vertical load-bearing elements called studs connected to a track, while the floors consist of horizontal load-bearing elements called joists connected to a ledger track. There are three primary methods for assembling walls and floors: platform, balloon, and ledger framing (1). These methods fall into Sequential or Continuous Construction Methods (SCM or CCM) categories, depending on the continuity of studs between levels. Platform framing constructs one level at a time, creating non-continuous wall studs. Balloon framing maintains continuous wall studs over one story, with floors suspended from walls using a ledger track. Ledger framing is a hybrid, constructing walls one level at a time but suspending floor joists from walls using a ledger track. In all approaches, floor joists connect to a ledger track or zed section, which in turn connects to wall studs via clip angles. This connection, categorized as a simple shear connection, allows the transfer of bearing forces on studs, with joist design primarily controlled by mid-span deflections under the serviceability limit state (2), resulting in deeper and heavier joist sections.

Ayhan and Schafer (3) explored the moment-rotation response of joist-to-stud connections in ledger framing through full-scale experiments. While the connection behaved similarly to a "simple" connection with sufficient rotation capacity, undesirable limit states including stud web crippling and ledger bottom flange at large rotations were noted. Sabbagh and Torabian (4) proposed a novel semi-rigid joist-to-stud connection, eliminating the need for ledger track and clip angles by screwing the joist web directly to the stud web. The semi-rigidity of the connection enables the utilization of lighter joist sections by mitigating mid-span deflections, a factor typically governing the design of joist elements. This connection, shown in *Fig. 1*, can be used in both continuous and sequential construction methods.

This study employs Finite Element (FE) modelling to investigate the behaviour of the novel semi-rigid joist-to-stud connection (*Fig. 1*) under various influential parameters, such as joist and stud sizes, screw configurations, and gravity loading. The web planar screwed connection is examined for stiffness, moment capacity, and governing failure mechanisms. Additionally, a case study design of a Light Steel Framed (LSF) building demonstrates the potential advantages of the novel semi-rigid connection over currently used simple shear connections.

Fig. 1. Novel joist to stud connection configuration adopted for SCM and CCM (4)

2 DESCRIPTION OF FE MODEL

In this study, Finite Element (FE) models were created for a novel semi-rigid connection as illustrated in *Fig. 2*. These models were developed in the ABAQUS (5) software package and incorporating considerations for geometric imperfections and material non-linearity.

2.1 Description of FE model

The FE model for the semi-rigid connection encompasses a screwed web connection between the lipped channel sections of joists and studs. A hard surface-to-surface contact was defined for all elements. The stud height, modelled as 2.7m, included a restraint in the out-of-plane direction (bridging) at mid-height using reference point RP-4 for SCM assemblies. For CCM, the connection was positioned at the mid-height of the stud. A hinged boundary condition was implemented at the bottom of studs using reference point RP-2, coupling all degrees of freedom of the stud end section. Gravity load from upper levels was applied through RP-3, coupled to the studs at the top with free translation and rotation in the vertical (Y-direction) and X-direction, respectively. Translation in the X direction was restrained at the connection location and sides of the sheathing, replicating practical restraints for floor connections in Cold Formed Steel (CFS) buildings.

The joist length of 3.3m was used in the models, representing half the length of floor joists in the CFS NEES building (6). This choice aligns with the experimental results used for validating FE model parameters, which are indicative of a joist-to-stud connection in the CFS NEES building. Cross-sectional imperfections were also incorporated into the model. A two-step loading process was employed. In step 1, the gravity load was applied at RP-3. In step 2, the model underwent analysis with static displacement imposed at the cantilevered end (RP-1 in Fig. 2) of the joist to induce moments in the joist-to-stud connection.

Fig. 2. FE model assembly for the semi rigid connection in SCM (left) and CCM (right)

2.2 Element Type and Material Properties

The modelling of steel joists, face tracks, stud channel sections, and OSB sheathing involves the use of shell elements. Following a mesh sensitivity analysis, a suitable mesh size of approximately 10x10 mm² was employed for all elements. Despite increased computing time, further mesh refinement has minimal impact on connection capacity behaviour. The steel is modelled by a bi-linear stress-strain curve with a nominal yielding strength of 345 MPa, modulus of elasticity of 203,500 MPa, and a strain hardening ratio 0.01. To provide necessary restraint to joist top flanges, OSB floor sheathing with a thickness of 14.9 mm and modulus of elasticity of 699 MPa is also modelled atop the joists.

2.3 Modelling of the Screws

The connection between the joist and stud web employs #12 self-drilling screws with a thread diameter of 5.4 mm. OSB sheathing is also connected using #12 screws to the top flanges of joists and the face track. Abaqus Point-based Cartesian Fasteners are used to model the screw connections with a radius of influence equal to the thread diameter of screws. This modelling technique, successfully applied in the FE modelling of Cold Formed Steel (CFS) connections (7), employs quad-linear load-deformation backbone curves for steel-to-steel and OSB-to-steel screw fasteners. These backbones are selected based on the work of Tao et al. (8), containing testing of screwed connections between steel sheathing of different thickness groups, including analytical formulations for predicting backbone curves.

More details on modelling assumptions can be found in (4). FE results on the proposed novel connection are further discussed in section 4.

2.4 Validation

As the models created here pertain to a new connection assembly yet to be tested, FE validation of modelling assumptions was conducted using available experimental results in the literature for ledger framed connections (3). FE models were developed for a ledger connection involving a single 1575 mm long joist connected to a ledger track with a $38 \times 38 \times 1.4$ mm clip angle. The ledger track is supported by two studs, each 813 mm high and 600 mm apart. *Fig. 3.* illustrates the test specimen for ledger framed connections tested at John Hopkins University (3).

Steel with a yield stress of 345 MPa was used for the joist, stud, ledger, and top track sections. These sections were represented by 1200S250-97 (304x64x15.9 mm, $t=2.5$ mm), 600S162-54 (152x41x12.7 mm, $t=1.4$ mm), 1200T200-97 (304x64 mm, $t=2.5$ mm), and 600T162-54 (152x4 mm, $t=1.4$ mm), respectively. OSB sheathing was affixed to the joist flange and the wall top track web. Simpson self-drilling #10 screws with a 4.7 mm thread diameter secured every connection. The load deformation behaviour of screwed connections was derived from (8).

Fig. 3 illustrates the dominant failure limit state of ledger flange buckling (LFB), consistent with both the FE model and the corresponding test (specimen T4 (3)). Moreover, as depicted in *Fig. 3*, the overall trend of moment-rotation behaviour estimated by FE analysis aligns well with the test results. Predictions for peak strength and initial stiffness from FE analysis are within 5% and 10% range of the test results, respectively. Additional details on FE validation are available in (4).

Fig. 3. Local Flang Buckling (LFB) observed in FE model for specimen T4 and Leger-framed connection test on specimen T4 (3); Comparison of moment rotation responses.

3 PARAMETERS UNDER INVESTIGATION

Following the validation of modelling assumptions as outlined in section 2.4, an investigation of the impact of various parameters on the response of the proposed connection was conducted. The primary objective of this parametric study was to observe different failure mechanisms and their associated moment-rotation responses in the proposed connection. The investigated parameters encompassed gravity loading from upper floor levels, screw arrangement on the connection, combinations of stud and joist thicknesses, and the type of construction method, as elaborated in the subsequent sub-sections.

3.1 Gravity Loading

Gravity loading from upper levels was applied to the studs to examine its effect on the connection response. Three different intensities of gravity loading were considered: 0%, 20%, and 40%. The 0% level denotes the absence of gravity load, while the 20% and 40% gravity loads are computed based on the 20% and 40% load-bearing capacity of studs. This assumption aligns with the typical design scenario where gravity load-bearing studs experience loads ranging from 20% to 40% of their capacities.

3.2 Screw Arrangement

Various planar screw arrangements were adopted to connect the webs of studs and joists. Specifically, 1 to 4 vertical lines of screws were utilized. Within each line, 3 rows of screws were

employed. The horizontal distances of the outermost lines of screws to the centre of gravity of the screw group were kept constant in the case of 2 to 4 lines of screw arrangements. All cases met the spacing requirement outlined in EN 1993-1-3 (9).

3.3 Joist and Stud Thicknesses

Different combinations of cross-sectional thicknesses for studs and joists were also investigated. Two levels of plate slenderness were used to joists, while studs had three different slenderness levels. The remaining dimensions for studs and joists, including cross-section depth, flange widths, lip sizes, and longitudinal dimensions, were kept constant.

3.4 Construction Method

The impact of employing the proposed novel connection in both Sequential Construction Methods (SCM) and Continuous Construction Methods (CCM) was also explored. Identical connection assemblies were adopted for both SCM and CCM configurations, as illustrated in *Fig. 2*.

Each modelled connection assembly is assigned an identifier tag based on the following nomenclature: The first letter represents the type of construction method (S for Sequential or C for Continuous). The first two numbers represent the thickness of the joist in one ten-thousandth of meters. The subsequent two numbers represent the thickness of the stud in one ten-thousandth of meters. A number followed by a dash (-) represents the number of lines of screws, and the number in decimal fraction followed by the second dash (-) represents the percentage of gravity load (for 0%, this number is not specified).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The outcomes of the Finite Element (FE) analysis were primarily scrutinized based on moment-rotation responses at the connection and the governing failure mechanisms. The analysis identified two primary failure modes: local buckling of the studs or failure of the joist-to-stud fastener, as depicted in *Fig. 4*. Joist yielding or buckling was not observed in any of the analysed cases.

Fig. 4. Failure mechanisms (Floor sheathing removed for sake of clarity)

The subsequent set of figures presents moment-rotation curves for various connection assemblies, revealing two distinct curve shapes. Connections lacking a post-peak response are influenced by the joist-to-studs connection failure, while those with a substantial post-peak response, truncated to a 20% drop after the peak moment, are governed by stud failure. All curves exhibit a consistent pre-peak pattern characterized by a bilinear slope leading up to the peak point.

Fig. 5. Moment rotation curves for all connection assemblies

4.1 Effect of Gravity Loading

The impact of gravity loading from upper floors on studs was analysed to assess the connection's sensitivity to it. The application of gravity loading increased the internal force in studs, making them more critical. On average, a moment capacity reduction of 11% was observed by adding gravity loads to connection assemblies. The initial stiffness of the connection assemblies, as compared in Fig. 6, averaged 997 kNm/rad and 547 kNm/rad for CCM and SCM connections, respectively, in the case of no gravity loading. The application of gravity loading deteriorated the initial stiffness by 7% and 16% for CCM and SCM connection assemblies, respectively. This deterioration in elastic stiffness is attributed to global buckling deformations in studs caused by the application of gravity loads.

Fig. 6. Effect of gravity load on initial stiffness of the connection

4.2 Effect of Screw Arrangements

Different screw arrangements were adopted in both CCM and SCM connection assemblies, with varying effects on stiffness and maximum bending moment capacities. Fig. 7. demonstrates the influence of screw lines on the bending moment capacities of the connections. Shifting from 3 to 4 lines of screws did not affect the bending capacity in some cases, where the joist-to-stud fastener failure mechanism governed the response. Transitioning from 1 to 3 lines of screws consistently increased the connection moment resistance. Therefore, 3 lines of screws could represent a threshold number in the proposed novel connection.

Fig. 7. Effect of screw lines on maximum moment capacities of connection

4.3 Effect of Joist and Stud Thicknesses

No distinct trend was observed for different combinations of thicknesses for studs and joists, as shown in previous figures. However, specimens with joist thickness less than or equal to stud thickness performed better in terms of moment resistance. This performance is attributed to the shift of the governing failure mechanism away from studs towards screws and possibly the joist in such connections. The stiffness of the connection remained unaffected by variations in the combination of joist and stud thicknesses, as the number of screws primarily governs the initial stiffness.

4.4 Effect of Construction Method

Transitioning to CCM from SCM did not improve the maximum bending moment capacity for connections with joist-to-stud fastener failure as the governing mechanism. However, in connections governed by stud failure, transitioning to CCM increased the maximum bending moment capacity by 23% on average. This improvement is likely due to the beneficial effect of stud continuity in CCM, offering better restraint at mid-height of studs.

5 CASE STUDY – BUILDING DESIGN EXAMPLE

To illustrate the advantages of utilizing the proposed joist-to-stud connections, a case study design for a typical six-story residential building in the UK was conducted. The building had dimensions of 12 m x 30 m, and each floor considered a dead load of 1 kN/m² and a live load of 2 kN/m². A wind speed of 22 m/s was taken into account, resulting in a maximum wind pressure of 1.02 kN/m². Additionally, an earthquake load with a peak ground acceleration of 0.15 g was assumed. The floors were constructed using lightweight concrete and were supported by joists spaced at 0.6 m. Cold-formed lipped channel sections were employed for both joists and studs, with a maximum clear span of 6 m for the joists and 3 m height for the studs at each story. Strap bracing was added to resist horizontal actions.

5.1 Structural Analysis

A 3D model of the building was created using the SAP2000 software package (10) to analyse the internal forces in the structural elements. The figure below illustrates typical bays of the building in the shorter direction along with a 3D model representation. A full lateral bracing was applied to the top flange of the joist, while mid-height lateral bracing was provided to both flanges of the studs, aligning with common practices in the design of Light Steel Frame (LSF) buildings. A rigid diaphragm constraint was applied to the joists. Strap bracing was modelled as a truss element, considering only the tension strap, as the compression strap would not resist lateral loads due to its slender nature. Lateral loads were only applied in the shorter direction, primarily to account for lateral displacement in the design of the gravity frame (unbraced bays) caused by wind and earthquake loadings.

The initial analysis assumed that the joists were pin connected to the studs, implying no moment transfer from joists to studs. Joists were designed against bending action due to the gravity load on the floor, while studs were designed solely against axial compression action. Under this assumption, a maximum bending moment of 11.74 kNm was obtained at the mid-spans of the joists.

Fig. 8. Case stud building models

The novel joist-to-stud connection introduces rotational stiffness to resist bending moments, estimated at 228 kN/m for sequential construction and 456 kN/m for continuous construction, based on average values obtained from FE modelling in ABAQUS (as explained in earlier sections). To assess the impact of this connection in a building model, rotational springs were incorporated at the joist ends, assigned initial stiffness derived from FE modelling. From elastic analysis, a 10% reduction in maximum mid-span moments for sequential connections and a 20% reduction for continuous semi-rigid connections compared to simple connections was observed. These reduced moments are then redistributed to the joist ends and ultimately transferred to the stud.

5.2 Structural Design

Considering internal forces from the elastic structural analysis, joists and studs were designed using Eurocode 3-Part 1-3: EN 1993-1-3 (9). For semi-rigid connections, studs were also designed against

end moments from joists. The structural design summary for three building models is presented in *Tables 1, 2, and 3*. The joist and stud steel material have a yield stress (f_y) of 355 MPa and ultimate stress (f_u) of 510 MPa. The structural design of the joist is always governed by deflection due to service loads. In the case of semi rigid connections, the capacity of studs was calculated considering moment and axial force interaction.

Table 1. Design of Building with pinned connections

Storey	Joists				Studs			
	M_{Ed} (kNm)	L/360 (mm)	Section (mm)	Deflection (mm)	D/C SLS	D/C ULS	Section (mm)	D/C ULS
6	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x1.4	0.37
5	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x1.4	0.65
4	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x1.6	0.76
3	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x1.6	0.86
2	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x2.0	0.76
1	11.7	16.6	300x89x18x2.5	12.7	0.76	0.45	150x75x15x2.0	0.96

Table 2. Design of Building with sequential semi rigid connections

Storey	Joists				Studs			
	M_{Ed} (kNm)	L/360 (mm)	Section (mm)	Deflection (mm)	D/C SLS	D/C ULS	Section (mm)	D/C ULS
6	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x1.4	0.23
5	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x1.4	0.81
4	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x1.6	0.56
3	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x1.6	1.00
2	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x2.0	0.84
1	10.5	16.6	300x75x15x2.0	15.2	0.92	0.58	150x75x15x2.0	0.89

Table 3. Design of Building with continuous semi rigid connection

Storey	Joists				Studs			
	M_{Ed} (kNm)	L/360 (mm)	Section (mm)	Deflection (mm)	D/C SLS	D/C ULS	Section (mm)	D/C ULS
6	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	150x75x15x1.4	0.67
5	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	150x75x15x1.4	0.86
4	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	150x75x15x1.6	0.89
3	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	150x75x15x1.6	1.00
2	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	180x75x15x1.8	0.89
1	9.6	16.6	300x75x15x1.8	15.2	0.91	0.60	180x75x15x1.8	0.95

5.3 Assessment of building performance with various connection types

The use of semi-rigid connections allows for lighter joist sections, reducing mid-span deflections and enabling the transfer of moments from mid-span to supports. Models with sequential and continuous semi-rigid connections exhibit lighter joist sections, resulting in a 22% reduction in steel weight for sequential connections and 28% steel savings for continuous connections compared to models with pinned connections. These outcomes underscore the material-saving benefits of the proposed semi-rigid connection, presenting valuable considerations for the construction industry.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper explores the behaviour of an innovative semi-rigid connection between a joist and a stud, achieved through screwing the web of the joist to the web of the stud. This design obviates the

need for ledger tracks and clip angles and is applicable in both continuous and sequential construction methods. The semi-rigidity of the connection enables the utilization of lighter joist sections by mitigating mid-span deflections, a factor typically governing the design of joist elements. The connection's response is analysed through Finite Element (FE) modelling, with validation conducted against experimental results from ledger framed connections in the literature.

A parametric study is then undertaken on the FE models to comprehend the impact of key parameters on the response of the semi-rigid connection. The parameters investigated include the presence of gravity loading from upper levels, screw arrangement on the connection, combinations of stud and joist thicknesses, and the type of construction method. The parametric analysis results indicate an average 11% reduction in connection moment resistance with the addition of gravity loads from upper story levels. This reduction is particularly noticeable when the stud is the weaker element of the connection, whereas it is less evident when the joist or screwed connection is the weaker element.

To exemplify the advantages of employing semi-rigid joist-to-stud connections, a case study design for a typical six-story residential building in the UK is conducted. The building model assumes either simply supported or semi-rigid joist-to-stud connections, with the latter assigned initial stiffness obtained from FE modelling. Implementing a sequential semi-rigid connection lead to a 22% reduction in the steel weight of the structure. Furthermore, the model with a continuous semi-rigid connection demonstrates a further 28% increase in steel savings. These findings underscore the material-saving benefits of adopting the suggested semi-rigid connection, offering significant advantages to the building sector.

REFERENCES

1. SCI Publication P402, Light Steel Framing in Residential Construction, 2015. 2015.
2. CEN. EN 1993-1-1 Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures-Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings. Brussels: European Committee for Standardization; 2005.
3. Ayhan D, Schafer BW. Cold-formed steel ledger-framed construction floor-to-wall connection behavior and strength. *J Constr Steel Res.* 2019 May;156:215–26.
4. Bagheri Sabbagh A, Torabian S. Semi-rigid floor-to-wall connections using side-framed lightweight steel structures: Concept development. *Thin-Walled Structures.* 2021 Mar;160:107345.
5. HKS. ABAQUS/standard users manual [Internet]. New York, USA: Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen Inc. (HKS).; 1996. Available from: <https://www.3ds.com/products-services/simulia/products/abaqus/>
6. Schafer BW, Ayhan D, Leng J, Liu P, Padilla-Llano D, Peterman KD, et al. Seismic Response and Engineering of Cold-formed Steel Framed Buildings. *Structures* [Internet]. 2016 Nov;8:197–212. Available from: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352012416300303>
7. Shahini M, Sabbagh AB, Davidson P, Mirghaderi R. Development of cold-formed steel moment-resisting connections with bolting friction-slip mechanism for seismic applications. *Thin-Walled Structures.* 2019 Aug;141:217–31.
8. Fannie Tao, Aritra Chatterjee, Christopher D. Moen. Report No. CE/VPI-ST-16-01 Monotonic and Cyclic Response of Single Shear Cold-Formed Steel-to-Steel and Sheathing-to-Steel Connections. 2016.
9. CEN. EN 1993-1-3 Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures-Part 1-3: General rules-Supplementary rules for cold-formed members and sheeting. Brussels: European Committee for Standardization; 2006.
10. CSI. Structural Analysis Program SAP2000 [Internet]. Berkeley, California, U.S.: Computers and Structures, Inc.; 2016. Available from: <https://www.csiamerica.com/products/sap2000>